

TABLE 1

Complex ^(a)		% V	% N	$\nu(V=O)$ cm ⁻¹
VO(sal-o aminobenzyl- alcohol)	Found	17.0	4.6	980
	Reqd.	17.47	4.79	
VO(5-br. mosal-o-amino- benzylalcohol)	Found	18.1	4.0	925
	Reqd.	18.75	3.77	
VO(5-methoxysal-o- aminobenzylalcohol)	Found	16.2	4.5	985
	Reqd.	15.84	4.35	
VO(3-ethoxysal-o- aminobenzylalcohol)	Found	15.4	4.2	925
	Reqd.	15.18	4.17	
VO(hydrox-o-aminobenzyl- alcohol)	Found	14.5	4.0	925
	Reqd.	14.91	4.09	

(a) Abbreviations: sal=salicylaldehyde, 5-bromosal=5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-methoxysal=5-methoxysalicylaldehyde, 3-ethoxysal=3-ethoxysalicylaldehyde and hydrox=2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde.

925-985 cm⁻¹ (see Table 1) and is in the usual range observed for many oxovanadium(IV) complexes⁸. The complexes are insoluble in common solvents and melt or decompose >250°. As the complexes are insoluble in common solvents it was not possible to find out molecular weights and degree of polymerisation of the complexes. The room temperature magnetic moments of the complexes as determined by the Gouy method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as a standard are in the range 1.3-1.5 B.M. The observed magnetic moments of the complexes are less than the spin-only moment of 1.73 B.M. expected for an S=½ system, which are attributed to the antiferromagnetic spin-spin exchange between the interacting VO²⁺ ions⁷, as are the cases with the oxovanadium(IV) complexes of comparable ligands⁶.

The ESR and cryomagnetic studies on the complexes are in progress and details will be reported in due course. The corresponding copper(II) complexes are also being studied in order to compare the magnetic behaviour of these S=½ systems.

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A Rapid Gravimetric Method for the Determination and Separation of Cadmium

(Miss) A. GUHA THAKURTA, B. DAS* and S. C. SHOME

Chemical Laboratory, Presidency College, Calcutta

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CADMIUM has been determined gravimetrically with a number of organic precipitants, but only a few of them¹⁻⁵ produce complexes suitable for direct weighing. In the present investigation 3-hydroxy 1,3-diphenyl triazine (HDPTA)⁶⁻⁸, a N-substituted phenylhydroxamic acid, has been employed for the direct determination of cadmium in small concentrations with a good degree of accuracy and for separation of the metal from a large number of diverse ions. The bright yellow precipitate of cadmium is obtained from solutions at pH 6.7-8.2 with HDPTA which is finely granular in texture and insoluble in hot water or 30% ethanol. The complex has been found to have the composition Cd(C₁₂H₁₀N₃O)₂.

Experimental

A solution of cadmium nitrate was prepared and standardised by the molybdate method. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared by dissolving known amounts of their pure compounds in water; dilute acids were added wherever necessary. The reagent (HDPTA) was prepared in the laboratory by the reaction between phenylhydroxylamine and benzene-diazonium chloride. A fresh 1% solution of recrystallized reagent in 95% ethanol was used for precipitation of cadmium.

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Procedure: A known aliquot of cadmium solution (6-41 mg of Cd) was taken in a beaker, diluted to 150 ml, 5-25 ml of the reagent solution were added into it dropwise and the pH was raised to 6.7-8.2 by adding 3M ammonia solution with constant stirring. The cadmium complex formed was allowed to settle at room temperature for 15-20 minutes with occasional stirring. The precipitate was filtered on a sintered bed glass crucible (No. 3), washed with warm (50°) 30% ethanol, dried at 110° and weighed to constant weight. The gravimetric factor used for the metal was 0.2089.

For complete precipitation of cadmium as the complex, at least 1.25 times the theoretical amount of the reagent was required. Use of large excess of the reagent produced high results.

Separation of Cadmium from Diverse Ions: Cadmium was precipitated with HDPTA in presence of Zn²⁺, Al³⁺, Sb³⁺, Bi³⁺ and As⁵⁺ using tartrate as

* Dept. of Agril. Chem. and Soil Science, B. C. K. V. V., Kalyani, West Bengal.

masking agent. Hg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ag^{1+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Mn^{2+} could be masked with 10% potassium cyanide solution, while Cd was precipitated as HDPTA complex after adding chloral hydrate as a demasking agent for the Cd-cyano complex. Cadmium was determined from a solution containing Fe^{3+} and Pb^{2+} by prior precipitation of the diverse ions with HDPTA at pH 4.0. Cadmium could be determined in presence of Sn^{2+} when the latter was first oxidized to Sn^{4+} and then masked with ammonium oxalate. The results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—INFLUENCE OF DIVERSE IONS ON THE DETERMINATION OF CADMIUM (Cd^{2+} taken = 6.86 mg)

Foreign ion (mg added)	Error (mg)	Foreign ion (mg added)	Error (mg)
Ag^{1+} (50)	+ .004	Fe^{3+} (80)	+ .003
Pb^{2+} (65)	+ .004	Sb^{3+} (70)	- .002
Zn^{2+} (75)	+ .001	Bi^{3+} (60)	+ .003
Hg^{2+} (80)	+ .002	AsO_4^{3-} (60)	+ .001
Cu^{2+} (93)	- .001	Sn^{2+} (90)	+ .004
Mn^{2+} (65)	- .003	F^- (80)	+ .002
Co^{2+} (60)	+ .001	CH_3COO^- (>100)	+ .002
Ni^{2+} (90)	+ .002	Tartrate	+ .003
		Oxalate	- .002
Al^{3+} (70)	- .001	Citrate	+ .003

Precision and Accuracy : The relative mean error and the relative standard deviation were found to be 0.24% and 0.32% respectively.

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A Simple Batch Dilatometer for Measurement of Excess Volumes

R. C. PALTA and B. S. LARK

Department of Chemistry, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar.
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A simple batch dilatometer for direct measurements of excess volumes of binary organic mixtures is described in figure 1. Limb A ends in a ground glass disc D with a pin hole in the centre and can be sealed with a ground teflon disc D' overlapped by metal disc D'' and clamp E. Limb B carries a calibrated capillary P at its top to register the volume change. The two components are taken in the two limbs separated by mercury M contained in connecting tube L. Volume of the component in limb B can

Fig. 1. A simple batch dilatometer

be adjusted by requisite amount of mercury contained in it. Two such dilatometers with bulb capacities around 2.5, 2.5 and 0.5, 4.5 cm^3 have been used to study the excess volumes of cyclohexane(1)+benzene for entire composition range. Requisite amount of pure, double distilled and thoroughly degassed mercury was placed in the connecting tube L and then 5-7 times, frozen degassed and melted samples were filled by means of hypodermic syringes carrying stainless steel needles, first one in limb A followed by sealing, weighing and then second in limb B. Purities of the liquids used were checked by determining their densities and refractive indices which agreed with the literature values very well. Temperature of the thermostat was controlled to $25 \pm .005^\circ$. The capillary P was calibrated at each centimetre point and volume change for an observed change in levels, was determined graphically. The $V_m^E(x)$ values observed for various compositions $x C_6H_{12} + (1-x) C_6H_6$ have been fitted to the following equation,

$$V_m^E = x(1-x)2.5887 - 0.1195(1-2x) + 0.0044(1-2x)^2 \dots (1)$$

The observed values of V_m^E along with their deviations (δV_m^E) from the corresponding calculated values from equation (1) are given in Table 1. Observed values have a root mean square deviation of $0.0013 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ which is of the order of